

Subject:

Political Science

Title:

A study on PMAY-G: A special reference to the state of Odisha

Author:

Debakanta Nayak**Research Scholar, Department of Political Science, Sambalpur University**

Abstract:

The Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana-Gramin (PMAY-G) aims to provide pucca houses with basic amenities to rural households, including marginalized communities in Odisha. Innovative approaches such as geo-tagging, disaster-resilient construction and community involvement have bolstered its implementation. Despite significant progress, challenges like fund delays, land disputes, and natural disasters persist. Solutions include technology integration, sustainable housing, and skill development programs. Linking PMAY-G with other schemes and fostering community participation further enhances its impact. PMAY-G has improved housing conditions, generated employment, and promoted social inclusion, contributing significantly to Odisha's rural development.

Keywords:

Rural housing, Odisha, PMAY-G, disaster resilience, community participation

LYCEUM INDIAJournal of **Social Sciences****Introduction:**

The Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana - Gramin (PMAY-G) is a flagship initiative by the Government of India, aimed at providing housing for all in rural areas by 2024. In Odisha, the program has been instrumental in improving the living conditions of economically weaker sections, particularly those from Scheduled Castes (SC), Scheduled Tribes (ST), and other marginalized communities. Implemented in collaboration with the state government, PMAY-G provides financial assistance to eligible beneficiaries to construct pucca (permanent) houses with essential amenities. Odisha has adopted innovative approaches such as geo-tagging for monitoring progress, community involvement, and the use of disaster-resilient construction techniques to cater to the region's unique challenges, including vulnerability to cyclones and floods. The scheme not only addresses housing shortages but also contributes to social inclusion and economic upliftment in rural Odisha.

Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (PMAY):

The Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (PMAY) is a flagship housing scheme launched by the Government of India in 2015 with the ambitious goal of providing "Housing for All" by 2022. This comprehensive housing policy aims to address the housing needs of the urban poor and economically weaker sections of society. PMAY operates in two components: PMAY-Urban, focusing on urban areas, and PMAY-Gramin, targeting rural areas. Under PMAY-Urban, beneficiaries from the Economically Weaker Sections (EWS), Low-Income Groups (LIG), and Middle-Income Groups (MIG) are eligible for various subsidies and credit-linked subsidies on home loans. PMAY-Gramin provides financial assistance to eligible rural households for construction or upgradation of their houses. The scheme has been instrumental in boosting the construction sector, generating employment opportunities, and improving the overall living standards of beneficiaries. However, challenges such as land acquisition, bureaucratic hurdles, and financial constraints have hindered its full potential. Despite these challenges, PMAY remains a significant step towards realizing the dream of a "Housing for All" in India.

The Objectives of PMAY-G

PMAY-G was launched with the objective of providing housing for all by 2022. The scheme introduced several innovative features, including:

- **Beneficiary-led Construction:** This approach empowers beneficiaries to take ownership of the construction process, leading to greater transparency and accountability.
- **Technology Integration:** The use of technology, such as mobile apps and GIS, has streamlined the implementation process and improved monitoring.
- **Focus on Quality and Sustainability:** PMAY-G emphasizes the construction of durable and sustainable houses, using locally available materials and energy-efficient technologies.

Present Context

As of the latest updates, Odisha has made significant progress under the **Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (PMAY)**, both in urban and rural areas:

1. **Rural Achievements:** Under PMAY-Gramin, Odisha has built over 36 lakh houses to provide permanent residences for the economically weaker sections living in rural areas. These houses are geo-tagged, ensuring transparency and tracking of the development process. The state has employed a systematic approach, ensuring inclusion by covering areas with tribal populations and other vulnerable groups.

2. **District-Wise Progress:** The district-wise progress is monitored and can be accessed through the official Rural Housing Odisha portal. The platform provides granular data by allowing users to check construction status down to the village level, ensuring accountability. For instance:

- **Ganjam District** and **Kalahandi District** have seen notable implementation with geo-tagged tracking of the houses built.
- **Deogarh** and **Jajpur** districts have also contributed significantly with consistent house completions.

3. **Urban Achievements:** In urban areas under PMAY-Urban, 1.3 lakh houses were constructed during 2022-2023, with plans to build 31,000 additional homes in 2023-2024. Odisha integrates innovative mechanisms such as slum rehabilitation under the **JAGA Mission** and **Beneficiary-Led Construction (BLC)** approaches to support sustainable urban housing. Award-winning municipalities like Choudwar and NACs of Kashinagar have been recognized for their exceptional efforts

4. **Funding and Policy Support:** The state has ensured efficient fund allocation and policy mechanisms for rapid implementation. Odisha has utilized grants and district mineral funds to extend housing programs to mining-affected regions and other economically backward areas

Key Challenges in PMAY-G Implementation in Odisha

1. Identification of Beneficiaries and Targeting:

- **Lack of Transparency and Accountability:** In some cases, there have been allegations of favoritism and corruption in the beneficiary selection process.
- **Incomplete Socio-Economic Census (SEC) Data:** Inaccurate or incomplete SEC data can lead to exclusion of eligible beneficiaries and inclusion of ineligible ones.
- **Geographical Disparity:** The scheme's reach in remote and tribal areas has been limited due to logistical challenges and lack of awareness.

2. **Financial Constraints and Delays in Fund Disbursement:**

- Delayed Fund Release: Delays in the release of funds from the central government to the state government and then to the beneficiaries have hampered the pace of construction.
- Insufficient Allocation: The allocated funds may not be sufficient to cover the actual cost of construction, especially in areas with high construction costs.
- Misappropriation of Funds: In some instances, there have been reports of misappropriation of funds by contractors or government officials.

3. **Construction Quality and Technical Issues:**

- Lack of Skilled Labor: A shortage of skilled labor, particularly in rural areas, can lead to subpar construction quality.
- Use of Substandard Materials: The use of substandard construction materials can compromise the durability and safety of the houses.
- Delayed Supervision and Monitoring: Inadequate supervision and monitoring of construction activities can result in poor workmanship and deviations from the approved plans.

4. **Land Acquisition and Legal Issues:**

- Land Disputes and Encroachment: Land disputes and encroachment on government or community land can delay the construction process.
- Legal Hurdles: Complex land acquisition procedures and legal formalities can hinder the timely acquisition of land for housing projects.

5. **Natural Disasters and Geographical Constraints:**

- Cyclones and Floods: Odisha is prone to natural disasters like cyclones and floods, which can damage or destroy houses under construction.
- Difficult Terrain: In hilly and remote areas, construction can be challenging due to difficult terrain and poor infrastructure.

Remedies and Practical Solutions

1. **Strengthening Beneficiary Identification and Targeting:**

- Transparent and Participatory Selection: Implement a transparent and participatory beneficiary selection process involving local communities and gram panchayats.
- Updating SEC Data: Regularly update the SEC data to ensure accurate identification of eligible beneficiaries.
- Geographical Targeting: Prioritize remote and tribal areas for focused implementation of the scheme.

2. **Improving Financial Management and Disbursement:**

- Timely Fund Release: Ensure timely release of funds from the central government to the state government and then to the beneficiaries.
- Adequate Allocation: Allocate sufficient funds to cover the actual cost of construction, especially in areas with high construction costs.
- Robust Monitoring and Accountability: Implement robust monitoring and accountability mechanisms to prevent misappropriation of funds.

3. **Enhancing Construction Quality and Technical Supervision:**

- Skill Development: Organize skill development programs for local masons and laborers to improve construction quality.
- Quality Control Measures: Implement strict quality control measures to ensure the use of standard materials and adherence to building codes.

- Regular Monitoring and Supervision: Conduct regular site visits and inspections to monitor construction progress and quality.
4. **Addressing Land Acquisition and Legal Issues:**
- Simplified Land Acquisition Procedures: Streamline land acquisition procedures and provide adequate compensation to land owners.
 - Legal Assistance: Provide legal assistance to beneficiaries to resolve land disputes and legal issues.
 - Community Engagement: Involve local communities in land acquisition and dispute resolution processes.
5. **Mitigating the Impact of Natural Disasters and Geographical Constraints:**
- Disaster-Resilient Housing: Design and construct houses that are resilient to natural disasters like cyclones and floods.
 - Appropriate Building Techniques: Use appropriate building techniques and materials suitable for the local climate and terrain.
 - Infrastructure Development: Improve road connectivity and other infrastructure facilities in remote and hilly areas.

Impact of PMAY-G on Odisha's Rural Landscape

PMAY-G has had a profound impact on the rural landscape of Odisha:

- **Improved Housing Conditions:** The scheme has significantly improved the housing conditions of millions of rural households, providing them with pucca houses with basic amenities.
- **Economic Empowerment:** The construction of houses has generated employment opportunities for local laborers and small-scale industries.
- **Social Empowerment:** Access to decent housing has empowered women and children, improving their health, education, and overall well-being.
- **Rural Development:** PMAY-G has contributed to the overall development of rural areas, leading to improved infrastructure and social services.

Future suggestions

1. Embracing Technology for Transparency and Efficiency

Technology can play a pivotal role in streamlining processes under PMAY-G in Odisha.

- **Use of GIS for Site Selection and Monitoring:** Geographic Information Systems (GIS) can be used to identify suitable land parcels for construction, especially in flood-prone or hilly regions of Odisha. For example, districts like Malkangiri and Koraput face challenges due to their topography. GIS-based planning can ensure houses are built in safe and accessible areas.
- **Blockchain for Fund Disbursement:** To address concerns regarding fund leakages and delays, blockchain technology could be introduced to create a transparent and tamper-proof system for financial transactions. This ensures direct benefit transfer (DBT) to beneficiaries without intermediaries.
- **Mobile Applications for Beneficiaries:** A user-friendly mobile app in Odia and tribal languages can assist beneficiaries in tracking application status, lodging grievances, and receiving construction updates. Similar apps implemented in other states have increased accessibility and trust among rural populations.

2. Enhancing Inclusivity and Outreach

While PMAY-G targets economically weaker sections, Odisha's diverse demographic requires a nuanced approach.

- **Focus on Tribal Populations:** Tribal districts such as Rayagada and Kandhamal often face exclusion due to lack of awareness or administrative hurdles. Special outreach programs with the help of local NGOs can bridge this gap. For instance, conducting camps in tribal villages with visual aids in their native languages can help them understand the application process better.
- **Women-Led Housing Initiatives:** Encouraging joint ownership of houses by women beneficiaries ensures gender equity. In Odisha, empowering women Self-Help Groups (SHGs) to participate in the construction process can enhance local employment and ownership. The Mission Shakti movement in Odisha could be a partner in this initiative.
- **Customized Designs for Vulnerable Groups:** Houses under PMAY-G should cater to the specific needs of the elderly, disabled, and single women. For example, a house in Puri district could incorporate ramps and anti-skid tiles for an elderly couple.

3. Promoting Green and Sustainable Housing

Given Odisha's vulnerability to cyclones and other natural disasters, sustainable housing solutions are crucial.

- **Use of Local and Eco-Friendly Materials:** In districts like Balangir and Nuapada, where traditional construction materials like mud and bamboo are prevalent, integrating these into modern designs can reduce costs and improve climate resilience. For instance, compressed stabilized earth blocks (CSEBs) can be used to combine durability with sustainability.
- **Renewable Energy Integration:** Providing solar panels for lighting and heating in PMAY-G houses can reduce energy costs and promote clean energy usage. This is particularly useful in remote villages of Gajapati where grid connectivity is limited.
- **Disaster-Resilient Structures:** Odisha frequently faces cyclones and floods. Strengthening PMAY-G houses with disaster-resilient designs, such as elevated foundations in flood-prone areas, will ensure long-term sustainability.

4. Strengthening Infrastructure and Basic Amenities

A house is more than just four walls; access to basic amenities is vital for a dignified life.

- **Linking PMAY-G with Other Schemes:** Convergence with schemes like the Jal Jeevan Mission for piped water supply and Saubhagya Yojana for electricity can ensure holistic development. For example, a PMAY-G house in Kendrapara should have access to clean drinking water, a functional toilet, and uninterrupted power supply.
- **Improving Road Connectivity:** Rural housing projects often face logistical challenges due to poor roads. The Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana (PMGSY) should be synchronized with PMAY-G to improve last-mile connectivity. Villages in Mayurbhanj and Keonjhar districts can benefit significantly from such integrated planning.
- **Provision for Livelihood Spaces:** Houses should include provisions for livelihood activities, such as small workshops or storage spaces, especially in regions where residents depend on agriculture or handicrafts.

5. Building Capacity and Enhancing Skill Development

Capacity building is essential for effective implementation of PMAY-G in Odisha.

- **Training Local Youth:** Introducing training programs on modern construction techniques can empower local youth and create employment opportunities. For instance, masons in Sundargarh could be trained in constructing disaster-resilient structures, enhancing both quality and speed of housing delivery.
- **Partnering with Technical Institutes:** Collaborations with institutions like IIT Bhubaneswar or local polytechnics can bring innovative designs and techniques into rural housing. They can also assist in regular audits to ensure quality control.
- **Promoting SHG-Led Construction:** Women-led SHGs can be trained to undertake housing projects, ensuring cost-effectiveness and community participation.

6. Strengthening Monitoring and Accountability Mechanisms

Robust monitoring mechanisms are critical to ensure the success of PMAY-G.

- **Real-Time Progress Tracking:** A centralized digital dashboard accessible to state officials and beneficiaries can track project progress. For example, live updates on house construction in districts like Kalahandi can identify bottlenecks and address them promptly.
- **Third-Party Audits:** Engaging independent agencies for periodic audits ensures transparency and accountability. Such audits can focus on aspects like quality of construction, fund utilization, and beneficiary satisfaction.
- **Grievance Redressal System:** An efficient grievance redressal mechanism with toll-free numbers and online portals in local languages can address complaints promptly. For example, a farmer from Sambalpur can report delays without traveling to district offices.

7. Encouraging Community Participation

Community involvement fosters ownership and ensures long-term sustainability.

- **Formation of Village Committees:** Committees comprising beneficiaries, local leaders, and officials can oversee implementation at the grassroots level. In districts like Bhadrak, such committees can ensure fair allocation and timely execution of projects.
- **Social Audits:** Conducting social audits at the panchayat level increases transparency. Beneficiaries can voice concerns, and the community can collectively assess the program's impact.
- **Crowdsourcing Innovations:** Encouraging communities to propose innovative housing designs suited to local needs can lead to better outcomes. For instance, fishermen in coastal areas of Odisha might suggest stilted housing to withstand floods.

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